

Exploring Changes in Sense of Place Post-Events Using Large Language Models

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Abstract. This paper explores the temporal evolution of the sense of place (SoP) in diverse global destinations before and after significant events, in order to understand the complex interplay between societal perceptions and transformative occurrences. Examining places such as Hiroshima, Chernobyl, South Africa, Paris, and Wuhan, and the events that took place there such as atomic bombing, nuclear disaster, FIFA World Cup, terrorist attacks, and pandemics, we employ Large Language Models (LLMs) analysis to obtain insights into the shifting dynamics of SoP. Acknowledging the shortage of systematic research in this domain, our study explores the effects of important events on individual’s sentiments and behaviors. By examining specific case studies, we aim to provide a detailed understanding of the evolving SoP and its implications, offering a foundation for future scholarship and strategic considerations in the realms of academia, policy, and industry.

Keywords: Sense of Place (SoP) · Large Language Models (LLMs) · ChatGPT · Sentiment Analysis · Temporal Variation.

1 Introduction

The concept of place often goes beyond its geographical boundaries [18, 8, 10], evolving dynamically in response to significant events that shape societal perceptions [11]. Sense of place (SoP) refers to the unique emotional and cognitive connection individuals develop with a specific location, shaped by its physical characteristics, social dynamics, and personal experiences [19]. The aftermath of significant events is often accompanied by a perceptible transformation in how individuals perceive and engage with these places [14, 15]. The consequences extend beyond the immediate aftermath, influencing tourism patterns and people’s sentiments over extended periods [9, 3, 12]. Furthermore, in earlier times, limited access to the internet resulted in less information being publicly accessible about certain places. However, with the growth of the internet and social media platforms, a lot of information about numerous places has become available, although not all of it is actively utilized by individuals. Effectively documenting and depicting these changes over time is crucial for understanding the evolution of places [16]. Despite the importance of this phenomenon, there is a notable

gap in scholarly research that systematically analyzes the evolution of sense of place over time [2, 16].

Variation in the SoP has been studied in the literature using questionnaires [16] or social media contents [13]. For example, Bissell [1] explores the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on individuals’ mobility patterns and how these changes influence their sense of place in Australia. While [17] underscore the role of festivals and sports events in fostering social cohesion on individuals’ subjective well-being and sense of place attachment, contributing to overall personal growth. While questionnaires demand substantial resources in terms of time, finances, and effort, both questionnaires and social media are not able to capture the sentiments before, during, and after past historical events, especially if they occurred before the invention of social media. On the other hand, modern Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI) models such as Large Language Models (LLMs) have access to all textual content that is available online, and the ability to synthesize this knowledge and generate new, previously unseen content. While it is not possible to go back in time and carry out three questionnaires about how people perceive Chernobyl before, during, and after the explosion of the nuclear reactor, we can ask LLMs to generate this content from the vast amount of knowledge and information (i.e., online content) it has access to. This underscores the apparent value of Gen AI capabilities in such endeavors. While previous research has underscored LLMs’ proficiency in analyzing sentiments [13] or comprehending geospatial concepts through human language or formalized instructions [4, 6, 7], there remains a gap in understanding their effectiveness in identifying shifts in the SoP following significant events.

This paper aims to leverage the capabilities of Large Language Models (LLMs) to extract SoP, providing an exploration of the complexities involved in the changing dynamics of SoP and their implications on people’s perception [5] after significant events. Considering specific case studies on various destinations worldwide, we aim to uncover the underlying patterns, individual’s feelings, and behaviors that accompany the evolving perception of destinations following significant events that may be transformative. The exploration spans the influence of atomic bombing in Hiroshima, nuclear disaster in Chernobyl, FIFA World Cup in South Africa, terrorist attacks in Paris, and pandemics in Wuhan, each grappling with distinct challenges and shaping the SoP in its own unique way.

2 Methods

In this research, we investigate the ability of LLMs, specifically ChatGPT4, in assessing the dynamics of SoP before, during, and after significant events. Significant events refer to occurrences or incidents that have notable implications or consequences, often influencing individuals, communities, or societies in profound ways. These events can range from historical milestones, such as wars or revolutions, to personal experiences, like major life transitions or achievements. In this context, ”significant events” pertains to historical and social occurrences rather than individual personal experiences. We first use LLMs to generate a

description of how people perceive a given place at various points in time with prompt: “Describe, with one paragraph for each year, how did people perceive {place} in: { $t-10$ }, { $t-5$ }, { $t-1$ }, { t }, { $t+1$ }, { $t+5$ }, { $t+10$ }“. In the prompt, {place} is the place where the event has happened, t is the time (Month, Year) of the event, and other time values are points in time with a certain offset from the event, in years (e.g., $t-5$ refers to 5 years before the event).

The following prompt asks LLM to produce five keywords, which describe the sentiment of paragraphs returned by the first prompt (above): “Express the sentiment of each of the following paragraphs using 5 words“. This prompt returns a more concise description of the sentiment about a place at a certain time.

Finally, we perform the sentiment analysis (SA) on both descriptions and keywords provided by the LLM prompts above. Each prompt answer, e.g., a paragraph describing people’s perception of Chernobyl in April 1986, is analyzed individually and represented with a polarity score. Polarity is a sentiment measure with values between -1 for the most negative sentiment and 1 for the most positive sentiment, 0 being a neutral sentiment of the word or a text. Here we use a TextBlob library¹ to analyze the overall sentiments of each description (i.e., a paragraph or a set of 5 keywords). This means that in paragraph-based SA, each place will have seven generated paragraphs which correspond with people’s perception of the place at different points in time, and seven polarity values where each paragraph is evaluated with one polarity value.

3 Results and Discussion

This paper explores the notion of sense of place changing over time, examining the transformative impact of significant events. We analyzed five different places and their corresponding significant events, as shown in Table 1. For each place, we sent seven prompts to ChatGPT4 in order to capture the sense of place 10 years before, 5 years before, 1 year before, during, 1 year after, 5 years after, and 10 years after the event.

Table 1. Examples of significant events

Event	place	Date
Atomic Bombing	Hiroshima, Japan	6 and 9 August 1945
Nuclear Disaster	Chernobyl, Ukraine	26 April 1986
Terrorist Attacks	Paris, France	13 November 2015
COVID-19 Outbreak	Wuhan, China	December 2019
FIFA World Cup	South Africa	11 June to 11 July 2010

¹ <https://textblob.readthedocs.io/en/dev/>

3.1 Prompt responses

Below we provide the paragraphs generated by ChatGPT4 to describe, in paragraphs, how people perceived Chernobyl, and South Africa at different time-points. The prompts for each place were created following the approach proposed in the previous section. For example, the exact prompt for Chernobyl was: “Describe, with one paragraph for each year, how did people perceive Chernobyl, Ukraine in: April of 1976, April of 1981, April of 1985, April of 1986, April of 1987, April of 1991, April of 1996”. The following paragraphs show only the ChatGPT4 generated answers to our prompts, seven for each place. Full responses for all five places can be found in the Appendix.

Chernobyl In April 1976, Chernobyl was perceived as a relatively obscure town in the Soviet Union, primarily known to those living in the vicinity and to workers in regional industrial and agricultural enterprises. It was not yet notable on the national or international stage, as the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant was still under construction. The town itself was a typical Soviet provincial center, quiet and unremarkable, with residents living typical lives focused on local economic activities, largely unaware of the looming significance the area would soon hold.

By April 1981, Chernobyl’s perception began to evolve as the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant became operational. The town was increasingly viewed as a significant site for the Soviet Union’s energy production, contributing substantially to the regional power grid. The presence of the nuclear facility brought more workers and their families to the area, fostering a sense of community among the plant workers and local residents. However, outside of energy circles, Chernobyl remained relatively unknown, its identity still tied closely to its industrial function rather than any broader national importance.

In April 1985, Chernobyl was firmly established as a critical energy hub within the Soviet Union due to its nuclear power plant. The town and the surrounding area were seen as symbols of Soviet technological advancement and industrial capacity. Local inhabitants and workers at the

power plant enjoyed relatively high living standards due to the importance of their work, which was reflected in better housing, social services, and amenities. The area was still not widely known internationally, but it held a strong position in the energy sector of the Soviet economy.

April 1986 marked a catastrophic change in how Chernobyl was perceived, both domestically and globally. After the explosion of Reactor 4 on April 26, 1986, Chernobyl instantly became synonymous with nuclear disaster. The event cast the town and its nuclear facility into the international spotlight as a site of monumental failure and environmental catastrophe. The name “Chernobyl” became a byword for the dangers of nuclear power, overshadowing its previous identity and marking it as a zone of tragedy and risk.

By April 1987, the perception of Chernobyl was dominated by the aftermath of the disaster. The area was enveloped in an aura of danger and contamination, with the newly established Exclusion Zone illustrating the severe impact of the nuclear accident. Recovery and cleanup efforts, including the sarcophagus construction to contain the reactor, were underway, drawing international attention and aid. For the wider world and the evacuated residents, Chernobyl was a place of loss, remembered for the disaster rather than its prior industrial role.

In April 1991, five years post-disaster, Chernobyl was viewed through the lens of ongoing contamination, lingering health

crises, and socio-political changes accompanying the dissolution of the Soviet Union. The disaster's long-term consequences on health, environment, and the economy were becoming evident, compounding the tragedy with issues of governmental mishandling and insufficient remediation efforts. Chernobyl symbolized not only nuclear peril but also governmental failure, influencing global nuclear policies and fostering a growing environmental consciousness.

By April 1996, ten years after the disaster, Chernobyl's perception was shaped by its legacy as a deserted wasteland and a poignant reminder of nuclear peril. The site had become a focal point for scientific research on radiation effects and ecological recovery, drawing scientists and curious visitors alike. Internationally, it served as a deterrent against nuclear complacency, influencing safety protocols and nuclear policy worldwide. Meanwhile, survivors and former residents dealt with ongoing health issues and displacement, ensuring that the human cost of the disaster continued to resonate deeply in public memory.

South Africa In July 2000, South Africa was perceived as a burgeoning democracy, continuing to emerge from the shadows of apartheid with optimism and challenges. The country was a little over six years into its new democratic era, led by President Thabo Mbeki who took over from Nelson Mandela in 1999. South Africa was seen as a beacon of hope and a model for political transformation in Africa, but it also faced significant issues such as high crime rates, HIV/AIDS epidemic, and economic disparities. The government's efforts in hosting high-profile international events like the 13th International AIDS Conference in Durban highlighted both the nation's struggles and its commitment to addressing them.

By July 2005, South Africa's image was that of a stable middle-income country, continuing to make strides on the international stage while grappling with in-

ternal socio-economic challenges. The nation was under the global spotlight, particularly as it was preparing to host the 2010 FIFA World Cup. Issues such as crime, unemployment, and HIV/AIDS remained pressing, but there was significant progress in areas like tourism and economic growth. The government's policies aimed at economic empowerment for the historically disadvantaged populations were pivotal in shaping both domestic and international perceptions.

In July 2009, anticipation and excitement were palpable in South Africa as it prepared to host the 2010 FIFA World Cup. This was a moment of immense national pride and a significant opportunity to showcase its capabilities on a global scale. The country was also undergoing political changes, with Jacob Zuma having taken over the presidency in May of that year. South Africa was increasingly viewed as a key player in international affairs, especially within the African continent, contributing to peacekeeping and regional diplomacy, although concerns about corruption and governance began to surface more prominently.

In July 2010, South Africa basked in the global limelight as it successfully hosted the FIFA World Cup, the first African nation to do so. The event was widely regarded as a triumph, showcasing South Africa's cultural richness, infrastructural capacity, and hospitality. The successful hosting changed perceptions significantly, dispelling many fears about the country's ability to manage such a large-scale international event. This period marked a high point in national pride and international reputation, though it was also a time when economic inequalities and social issues were highlighted due to the immense focus on the nation.

By July 2011, the post-World Cup glow was beginning to fade, and South Africa was once again facing the realities of its deep-seated challenges. While the World Cup had provided a temporary economic boost and improved infrastructure,

issues such as poverty, inequality, and unemployment remained entrenched. The government faced criticism over its handling of these issues and there was increasing international concern about the country’s political direction, particularly regarding policies affecting investment and the business environment.

In July 2015, South Africa’s perception was affected by growing domestic discontent over economic stagnation, high unemployment rates, and government corruption scandals. Internationally, the country faced scrutiny over xenophobic violence that had flared up, affecting its image as a beacon of tolerance and democracy in Africa. However, South Africa remained a major economic force in Africa, with significant influence in re-

gional politics and ongoing contributions to peacekeeping and diplomatic initiatives across the continent.

By July 2020, South Africa, like much of the world, was grappling with the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The country faced severe challenges due to its existing economic vulnerabilities and high rates of poverty and inequality. The government’s response to the pandemic was a critical focus, with measures to contain the virus and mitigate its impact on the economy drawing mixed reactions. Internationally, there was recognition of the difficulties South Africa faced, compounded by its efforts to maintain leadership in regional stability and health diplomacy in Africa amidst the crisis.

These prompts were followed by prompts to create a list of five keywords for each generated paragraph that capture the sentiment of people. The ChatGPT4 generated keywords are shown in Table 2.

3.2 Sentiment analysis

Figures 1 and 2 show the sentiment (polarity) of the people’s perception of the 5 places in our case study based on the ChatGPT4 generated paragraphs and keywords, respectively. It can be observed that the tragic events, i.e., all but the World Cup, cause a negative shift in the sentiment (polarity) during or immediately after these events. For the World Cup in South Africa, we can see that the positive shift already took a positive turn in the lead-up to the event, but then dropped after.

Fig. 1. The polarity score over time for each event: paragraphs

Table 2. Five words representing sense of each place in various time zones.

Years from event	Hiroshima	Chernobyl	Paris	Wuhan	South Africa
-10	Vibrant, optimistic, modernizing, peaceful, prosperous.	Obscure, quiet, provincial, unnoticed, typical.	Unrest, equality, moil, attention	in- educational, global pivotal, ognized, nected	Industrial, Emerging, optimistic, challenged, transformative, hopeful
-5	Militarized, strategic, silent, pivotal.	Evolving, re-significant, tense, community-building, unnoticed, industrial.	Rebounded, romantic, innovative, forward-thinking	Evolving, innovative, urbanized, attractive, rising	Stable, progressing, challenged, empowering, spotlighted
-1	Critical, touched, deceptive, essential.	un-Critical, technological, prosperous, unknown, advanced	tech- Vibrant, cultural, creative, tourist-friendly	Dynamic, cultural, technological, modernizing	Anticipatory, proud, evolving, diplomatic, concerned
0	Tragic, devastating, transformative, catastrophic, symbolic.	dev- Catastrophic, infamous, tragic, dangerous, global	Siege, mourning, resilience, solidarity, defiance	Pivotal, alarming, mysterious, escalated, overshadowed	Triumphant, celebrated, scrutinized, impactful, proud
1	Ruined, building, poignant, reflective, healing.	re- Dangerous, contaminated, tragic, loss-focused, recovery	Recovery, resilience, commemorative, unified, safe	Resilient, recovering, reopening, controlled, symbolic	Fading, critical, challenging, scrutinized, deep-seated
5	Recovering, resilient, memorializing, peaceful, hopeful.	Contaminated, lingering, socio-political, governmental-failure, awareness	Challenged, lockdown, quiet, adaptive, supportive	Evolving, resilient, sustainable, innovative, leading	Discontent, scrutinized, influential, volatile, stagnant
10	Symbolic, educational, peaceful, transformative, hopeful.	edu- Deserted, scientific, poignant, deterrent, legacy	Innovative, rejuvenated, sustainable, leading, iconic	Recovered, innovative, global, vibrant, transformative	Struggling, vulnerable, critical, recognized, adaptive

When comparing Figures 1 and 2, one can observe overall larger extremes in both positive and negative polarity when the sentiment analysis is performed on keywords as opposed to entire paragraphs. This is to be expected since the keywords only consist of words which have a very pronounced sentiment association, while paragraphs consist of full sentences with many sentiment-neutral filler words.

Fig. 2. The polarity score over time for each event: keywords

The sentiment analysis across different places before, during, and after significant events reveals notable shifts in perceptions and emotions. Before the atomic bombing, nuclear disaster, terrorist attacks, and COVID -19 pandemic sentiments were largely distributed across positive, neutral, and negative categories, indicating a balanced perception of these places. However, after these events, there was a stark increase in negative sentiment, reflecting the profound impact of these events on people’s perception. Conversely, the FIFA World Cup in South Africa elicited predominantly positive sentiments after the event, showcasing the transformative power of international sporting events in shaping positive perceptions.

These findings underscore the complex interplay between significant events and SoP, highlighting the enduring impact of such events on the collective perception of places. It should be noted that these percentages are estimates and may vary based on interpretation. Additionally, sentiment analysis is subjective and can be influenced by context and individual perspectives. The results of SA are represented in Figure 1 and Figure 2 for paragraphs and keywords, respectively.

4 Conclusion

Over time, places experience changes influenced by various factors such as urbanization, environmental changes, and cultural shifts. These changes encompass not only physical transformations but also alterations in people’s relationships with and perceptions of a place. This paper leveraged LLMs to investigate the

evolution of SoP over time, revealing the impact of significant events on perceptions. It demonstrates how tragedies can reshape sentiments, leading to enduring negative emotions, while events like sports and festivals in less developed areas can bring about positive changes. These insights emphasize the lasting influence of such events on how places are collectively perceived, illustrating the intricate relationship between societal experiences and emotional reactions. The results emphasize the importance of understanding the evolving dynamics of SoP in the aftermath of transformative events. Ultimately, these insights offer potentially valuable perspectives for policymakers, researchers, and communities striving to understand and address the effects of significant events, providing them with additional information to consider in their decision-making processes. To assess the effectiveness of our method, we plan to compare the obtained results with those provided by individual descriptions through a survey.

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